

Corrosion inhibition of mild steel in aqueous binary solution of aggressive ions[†]

D. Prasad, G. S. Jha, B. P. Choudhary and S. Sanyal*

Department of Post Graduate Studies in Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj-816 109, India

Manuscript received 31 January 2001, revised 16 July 2001, accepted 22 August 2001

The effectiveness of sodium benzoate as corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in aqueous binary solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate has been studied. The inhibitor appears to function through adsorption following Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The thermodynamic parameters have been calculated. Polarization studies show that benzoate is an anodic inhibitor. Higher polarization of the anodes at low current densities indicates film formation on the metal surface.

Mild steel has been extensively used under different conditions in chemical and allied industries in handling alkalies, acids and salt solutions. Its corrosion studies are of immense interest due to widespread use in cooling water systems. Chloride, sulfate and nitrate ions in aqueous media are particularly aggressive and accelerate corrosion. Sodium benzoate has been reported as inhibitor for iron and steel dissolution reaction¹⁻³. In the present study an attempt has been made to evaluate the corrosion of mild steel and the influence of sodium benzoate on it in aqueous binary solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate.

Results and Discussion

The mixture of 60 parts (by vol.) sodium chloride and 40 parts (by vol.) sodium sulfate (both $10^{-1}M$), being most corrosive for mild steel⁴, was selected for further studies under different operating conditions.

Effect of inhibitor concentration : The result of effect of inhibitor concentration in aqueous solution of binary aggressive ions is given in Table 1. The metal loss progressively decreased with the rise in concentration of benzoate. The potentials were also ennobled in the presence of inhibitor, indicating the influence of the inhibitor with anodic partial process. There is no quantitative relationship between percentage inhibition efficiency and shift in the positive direction of potential.

Effect of aggressive ion concentration : Table 2 shows the weight-loss of mild steel in different concentrations (10^{-4} – $10^{-1}M$) of binary solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate. The corrosion rate increases with concentration of aggressive ions – both with and without inhibitor. However, complete protection of metal can be achieved at higher concentration (3%) of the inhibitor.

Effect of period of immersion : Weight-loss of metal for various periods of immersion (5–20 days) in $10^{-1}M$ binary

Table 1. Effect of inhibitor concentration on corrosion of mild steel in $10^{-1}M$ solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate at $20 \pm 2^\circ$ for 20 days

Concn. of benzoate %	Weight-loss $mg\ dm^{-2}$	Potential mV	Efficiency %
0	804.87	-670	–
0.05	118.89	-442	85.22
0.1	72.03	-320	91.05
1.5	42.46	-210	94.05
1.0	21.19	-186	97.37
1.5	11.12	-94	98.61
2.0	8.46	-52	98.94
2.5	2.98	-26	99.62
2.75	Nil	-12	100.00
3.0	Nil	+32	100.00

solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate with and without inhibitor is shown in Table 3. Benzoate is effective in long test duration to get good protection of metal.

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature (30 – 80°) on the corrosion of mild steel in the presence of benzoate in $10^{-1}M$ binary solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate is shown in Table 4. The corrosion rate increases with temperature of the corroding medium (with and without inhibitor), while the inhibitor efficiency decreases with rise in temperature. This may be due to the desorption of the adsorbed inhibitor molecules at higher temperatures and thus exposing the metal surface to further attack⁵.

Nature of adsorption and thermodynamic parameters : The activation energies calculated from rectilinear Arrhenius plots are $11.69\ kJ\ mol^{-1}$ for $10^{-1}M\ NaCl + Na_2SO_4$, $15.55\ kJ\ mol^{-1}$ for $10^{-1}M\ NaCl + Na_2SO_4 + 0.03\%$ benzoate and $19.14\ kJ\ mol^{-1}$ for $NaCl + Na_2SO_4 + 0.05\%$ benzoate. It appears that the activation energy of the corrosion reaction

[†]Paper presented in the 37th Annual Convention of Chemists 2000, held at Hardwar.

Table 2. Effect of concentration of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate on corrosion of mild steel containing sodium benzoate at $20 \pm 2^\circ$ of 20 days*

Concn. of NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i>	Weight-loss (mg dm ⁻²)			
	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ + 0.03% benzoate	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ + 0.05% benzoate	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ + 3% benzoate
10-4	588.12	59.72 (90.01)	31.22 (94.69)	Nil (100.00)
10-3	656.87	100.12 (84.75)	60.02 (90.86)	Nil (100.00)
10-2	741.48	141.29 (80.94)	79.26 (89.31)	Nil (100.00)
10-1	84.87	197.72 (75.43)	118.89 (85.22)	Nil (100.00)

*Values in parenthesis represent percentage inhibition.

Table 3. Effect of period of immersion on the corrosion of mild steel in $10^{-1}M$ solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate containing benzoate at $20 \pm 2^\circ$

Time (days)	Weight-loss (mg dm ⁻²)			
	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ +0.03% benzoate	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ +0.05% benzoate	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ + 3% benzoate
5	197.56	34.79 (82.39)	18.06 (90.85)	Nil (100.00)
10	439.02	88.91 (79.74)	46.67 (89.13)	Nil (100.00)
15	652.64	138.94 (78.67)	81.63 (87.47)	Nil (100.00)
20	804.87	197.72 (75.43)	118.89 (85.22)	Nil (100.00)

*Values in parenthesis represent percentage inhibition.

is higher in presence of inhibitor and is a function of inhibitor concentration. This also indicates that the adsorption is physical (weak) in nature on the metal surface⁶. The adsorption of inhibitor causes an increase in the activation energy of the process⁵ which leads to the conclusion that probably the inhibitor is bound to the surface by specific adsorption process and as a result of which a surface film of the reaction product is formed on the metal surface resulting in inhibition. This act of inhibition is probably hindered at elevated temperature due to the desorption of the inhibitor molecules.

To examine the adsorption behavior of the inhibitor, the data have been fitted to the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. A typical straight-line plot was obtained supporting Langmuir adsorption isotherm.

The methods of calculation of the values of heat of adsorption (Q), free energy of adsorption (ΔG) and entropy of

adsorption (ΔS) are the same as reported earlier⁷ and are given in the Table 5 along with the values of surface coverage (θ). The negative values of free energy of adsorption show strong interaction of inhibitor molecules⁸ and spontaneous adsorption on the metal surface⁹. Relatively smaller value of heat of adsorption indicates that the adsorption of inhibitor occurs easily and may be of physical (weak) type¹⁰. Increase in activation energy in presence of inhibitor and small values of free energy of adsorption are also indicative of weak (physical) adsorption of inhibitor on the metal surface¹¹.

Polarization study : The results of polarization measurements – both cathodic and anodic – for mild steel in $10^{-1}M$ solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate in presence and absence of inhibitor reveal that in absence of inhibitor there is both cathodic and anodic polarization. It was also noticed that there is no appreciable change in the

Table 4 Effect of temperature on corrosion of mild steel in $10^{-1}M$ solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate containing benzoate for one day*

Temp °C	Weight-loss (mg dm^{-2})			
	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ + 0.03% benzoate	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ + 0.05% benzoate	NaCl + Na ₂ SO ₄ + 3% benzoate
20	48.29	12.86 (73.33)	10.02 (79.20)	Nil (100.00)
40	69.33	19.79 (71.45)	14.63 (78.89)	Nil (100.00)
60	102.06	32.67 (67.99)	26.36 (74.17)	Nil (100.00)
80	241.39	82.09 (65.99)	64.18 (73.18)	Nil (100.00)

*Values in parenthesis represent percentage inhibition

Table 5 Values of surface coverage and other thermodynamic parameters of adsorption of benzoate at different temperatures in $10^{-1}M$ solution of sodium chloride and sodium sulfate for one day containing 0.05% benzoate

Temp °C	Surface coverage (θ)	ΔG kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	Q kJ mol^{-1}
20	0.7920	14.70	66.41	
40	0.7889	15.66	65.23	4.76
60	0.7417	15.93	62.13	
80	0.7318	16.74	60.90	

cathodic polarization in presence of inhibitor, but the anodic polarization is considerably increased. Higher polarization of the anode at low current densities indicates film formation at the anode sites. This infers that the protective effect of benzoate appears to be due to the formation of an insoluble film by benzoate appears to be due to the formation of an insoluble film by benzoate^{3,6,12}. An inhibitive film of basic benzoate is reported^{3,13} to form on the electrode surface which blocks oxidation of metal and thus retards the corrosion rate. Hence, the mechanism of inhibition is due to the blockage of the anodic sites first by adsorption which enables the formation of a protective insoluble film³.

Experimental

The experimental details are the same as described earlier¹². All the potentials were recorded against saturated calomel electrode (SCE).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.S.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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